

Studies on Hydrated Stannic Oxide. Part IV. Electrophoretic Behaviour of Anions on Hydrated Stannic Oxide Impregnated Papers

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Manuscript received 24 November 1978, revised 23 March 1979, accepted 18 June 1979

Electrochromatographic studies of some anions on hydrated stannic oxide impregnated papers have been carried out. Various background electrolytes were used for these studies at fixed potential differences and time intervals. On the basis of the differential mobilities of the anions, which depends on the ion-exchange properties of hydrated stannic oxide and the nature of complexes formed with the electrolytes, some useful binary separations have been achieved.

ELECTROCHROMATOGRAPHIC studies of some cations using hydrated stannic oxide¹ and thorium phosphate² impregnated papers have been reported from our laboratory. Some useful and highly selective separations of cations present in a binary or multicomponent solution have been observed. Since hydrated stannic oxide acts as a cation exchanger³ as well as an anion exchanger⁴, our work has been extended to the study of the electrochromatographic behaviour of some anions on hydrated stannic oxide impregnated paper. No such work using either hydrated stannic oxide or any other oxide has been reported so far. In our laboratory, we have prepared crystalline hydrated stannic oxide of composition $\text{SnO}_2 \cdot 2.1\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (batch 2)⁵ which is suitable for paper chromatographic studies⁶. In this paper, electrochromatographic behaviour of nine anions on hydrated stannic oxide impregnated paper are discussed. In order to determine the role of the ion exchanger in these studies, the same operation was repeated with ordinary Whatman No. 1 paper under identical conditions. Some difficult and interesting separations have been achieved.

Experimental

Apparatus :

Electrophoresis was carried out in a horizontal apparatus (Toshniwal, India, Type CMO1/0 Sl. No. 124).

Reagent :

Reagent grade sodium stannate (USSR) was used. All other reagents were either E. Merck or BDH analar grade. Whatman No. 1 chromatographic paper (45×2.5 cm) was used for electrophoretic work.

Ion-exchange papers was prepared as described previously¹. It has been observed that hydrated stannic oxide is insoluble in all the background electrolyte solutions used. Solution of sodium, potassium or ammonium compounds of anions were prepared (anions, 4 mg/ml).

Background electrolytes :

Seven background electrolyte solutions were used for electrophoretic work :

- (i) 0.05 M HCl + 0.09 M KCl (pH=2) ;
- (ii) 0.1 M Citric acid (pH=2.1) ; (iii) 0.1 M $\text{CH}_3\text{-COOH} + 0.1 \text{ M } \text{CH}_3\text{COONa}$ (pH=4) ; (iv) 0.1 M EDTA disodium salt (pH=5) ; (v) 0.1 M $\text{CH}_3\text{COOH} + 0.1 \text{ M } \text{CH}_3\text{COONa}$ (pH=6) ; (vi) 0.1 M $\text{NH}_4\text{OH} + 0.1 \text{ M } \text{NH}_4\text{HCl}$ (pH=8) ; (vii) 0.1 M $\text{NH}_4\text{OH} + 0.1 \text{ M } \text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$ (pH=10)

Detection Reagents

- (i) 1% ethanolic diphenyl carbazide solution : Cr(VI) ; (ii) 4.5% solution of ammonium molybdate in HNO_3 : P(V), AS(V) ; (iii) 4% FeCl_3 in 0.01M HCl solution : $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$, SCN^- ; (iv) 4% FeSO_4 in 0.01 M H_2SO_4 solution : $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$; (v) 20% $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 + 1\% \text{H}_2\text{O}_3$: V(v) ; (vi) 25% SnCl_2 solution in Conc. HCl : W(VI) ; (vii) 5% SnCl_2 solution in 3M HCl : Mo(VI).

Procedure :

Clean and dried electrode vessels were filled with equal volume of aqueous background electrolyte and electrolysis was carried out by the usual procedure (1, 2). A potential difference of 200 volt was applied for one hour. In the case of background electrolyte (No. vii) the potential difference was reduced to 100 volt, because higher voltages caused ignition and burning of paper. The migration

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TABLE 1—MOVEMENT (cm) OF ANIONS IN DIFFERENT BACKGROUND ELECTROLYTES ON HYDRATED STANNIC OXIDE PAPERS AND ON ORDINARY WHATMAN NO. 1 PAPERS (IN PARENTHESIS) TIME ALLOWED—ONE HOUR, POTENTIAL DIFFERENCE APPLIED—200 VOLT

Anions Studied	0.05M HCl + 0.09M KCl pH=2.0	0.1M Citric Acid pH=2.1	0.1M CH ₃ COOH + 0.1M CH ₃ COONa pH=4.0	0.1M EDTA pH=5.0	0.1M CH ₃ COOH + 0.1M CH ₃ COONa pH=6.0	0.1M NH ₄ OH + 0.1M NH ₄ Cl pH=8.0	0.1M NH ₄ OH + 0.1M NH ₄ Cl pH=10.0*
P(V)	0.0(0.0)	0.0(+1.0)	0.0(+2.1)	0.0(+1.6)	+0.4(+1.6)	+0.9(+1.7)	+0.5(+1.2)
As(V)	0.0(0.0)	0.0(+0.6)	0.0(+2.0)	0.0(+2.0)	0.0(+1.5)	+0.3(+1.6)	0.0(+0.8)
V(V)	0.0(-1.6)	0.0(+0.5)	0.0(+2.2)	+1.0(+1.8)	0.0(+1.5)	0.0(+3.5)	0.0(+1.5)
Mo(VI)	0.0(0.0)	0.0(+2.0)	0.0(T)	+0.8(+2.5)	0.0(+1.5)	+2.1(+3.6)	+1.2(+1.4)
W(VI)	0.0(+1.2)	0.0(+3.2)	0.0(+1.0)	0.0(+2.0)	0.0(+1.7)	0.0(+3.6)	+0.5(+1.5)
Cr(VI)	+2.0(+3.0)	+1.0(+1.5)	+0.5(+2.4)	+1.0(+3.1)	+1.4(+3.2)	+2.7(+4.0)	+1.4(+2.2)
SCN ⁻ Decomposed	(Decomposed)	+3.6(+4.5)	+3.0(+5.0)	+2.4(+3.4)	+2.7(+3.9)	+2.5(+3.4)	+1.5(+1.7)
Fe(CN) ₆ ⁴⁻	+2.0(+4.0)	T(+2.9)	+0.5(+3.5)	D(+2.7)	+1.5(+2.5)	+1.8(+2.5)	+1.1(D)
Fe(CN) ₆ ³⁻	+2.9(+4.0)	+2.5(+3.8)	+2.0(+3.0)	+3.7(+4.5)	+1.6(+3.5)	+1.0(+4.5)	+1.2(+2.3)

T=Trailing, D=Diffused. * 100 volt used.

Note: +sign=migration towards anode; -sign=migration towards cathode.

of anions towards the electrodes was noted by measuring the spot from the point of application to the middle of the zone. On the basis of the results observed in the case of individual anions, the experiment was repeated with synthetic binary mixture of particular anions of interest for separations.

Results and Discussion

Electrochromatography of anions with papers impregnated with ion-exchange materials plays an important role in the field of separation science. Exchange properties of these materials in combination with electrophoretic migration of anions yield useful binary separations.

Electrochromatographic behaviour of some differently charged anions has been studied with seven different background electrolytes on hydrated stannic oxide impregnated papers as well as on ordinary Whatman No. 1 papers for comparison. The results are given in Table 1.

The migration of the anions on ordinary Whatman No. 1 papers are given in parentheses in Table 1. The rate of migration on an impregnated paper under a given potential difference depends on the size and charge of the components, relative molecular mass, electrolyte concentration and adsorption on the exchanger (hydrated stannic oxide). Strongly adsorbed anions have low rate of migration.

The migrations of Cr(VI), Mo(VI), PO₄²⁻ and Fe(CN)₆⁴⁻ on impregnated papers are found to increase with the increase of pH of the background electrolytes and are in good agreement with adsorption and elution behaviour of those anions on hydrated stannic oxide. Similar behaviour is not observed with other

anions studied. The migration of Fe(CN)₆³⁻ (K_a=0.8 at pH≈4) on impregnated papers decreases with the increase of pH of the background electrolytes. The reverse is observed on ordinary Whatman No. 1 papers. That might be due to formation of insoluble stannic ferricyanide. The migration behaviour of SCN⁻ (K_a=8.8 at pH≈4) on both ordinary Whatman No. 1 papers and impregnated papers are similar. It decreases with the increase of pH of the electrolytes. The migration values of As(V), V(V) and W(VI) on impregnated papers are zero either might be due to strong adsorption or due to insoluble salt formation.

It is interesting to note from pH vs M₁ [M₁=migration of ion on ordinary paper - migration of ion on impregnated paper] curves (Fig. 1) that some anions such as P(V), As(V), Cr(VI) and Fe(CN)₆⁴⁻ have high M₁ values (i. e., adsorbed strongly by hydrated stannic oxide) in acetate buffer (pH=4) and their M₁ values decrease with increase of pH of the background electrolytes. The increased migration of Mo(VI) and W(VI) on ordinary Whatman No. 1 paper increase their M₁ values.

Fig. 1. Plot of M₁-value vs pH of the background electrolytes.

TABLE 2—SEPARATIONS ACHIEVED ON HYDRATED STANNIC OXIDE IMPREGNATED PAPER BY ELECTROCHROMATOGRAPHIC TECHNIQUE

Background electrolyte	Potential Difference applied	Time allowed	Separations achieved
0.05M HCl+0.09M KCl (pH=2.0)	200 volt	one hour	Fe(CN) ₆ ⁴⁻ (0.0) - Fe(CN) ₆ ³⁻ (+2.8)
0.1M Citric acid (pH=2.1)	200 volt	one hour	W(VI)(0.0) - Fe(CN) ₆ ⁴⁻ (+2.5)
0.1M CH ₃ COOH+0.1M CH ₃ COONa (pH=4.0)	200 volt	one hour	Fe(CN) ₆ ⁴⁻ (0.0) - SCN ⁻ (+3.0)
0.1M CH ₃ COOH+0.1M CH ₃ COONa (pH=6.0)	200 volt	one hour	Cr(VI)(+1.5) - SCN ⁻ (+2.8)
0.1M NH ₄ Cl+0.1M NH ₄ OH (pH=8.0)	200 volt	one hour	W(VI)(0.0) - Mo(VI)(+1.8); W(VI)(0.0) - Cr(VI)(+2.5); V(V)(0.0) - Mo(VI)(+1.9); V(V)(0.0) - Cr(VI)(+2.8) V(V)(0.0) - SCN ⁻ (+2.0); P(V)(+0.6) - Cr(VI)(+2.1) P(V)(+0.5) - SCN ⁻ (+2.3)
0.1M NH ₄ OH+0.1M NH ₄ Cl (pH=10.0)	100 volt	one hour	W(VI)(+0.5) - SCN ⁻ (+1.5); W(VI)(+0.2) - Fe(CN) ₆ ⁴⁻ (+1.3); P(V)(0.0) - Mo(VI)(+1.6)

From the Table 1, it is evident that the anions which are not adsorbed can be separated from various anions. Some useful binary separations are given in Table 2. The figure within the parenthesis denotes the distance (cm) travelled by the anions. It is interesting to note that the migration value of Fe(CN)₆⁴⁻ on impregnated paper at pH 2 (0.05 M HCl+0.09 M KCl) is +2.0 cm. But when it is mixed with Fe(CN)₆³⁻ its migration value is reduced to zero. It might be due to interaction with each other [K_a of Fe(CN)₆⁴⁻ is 15 at pH≈4]. Their separation is achieved at pH 2 and 4, and there is no separation at higher pH. The binary anion separations, which are achieved on both ordinary Whatman papers and impregnated papers, are not shown. A little or no effect is noted with citric acid or with disodium salt of EDTA as background electrolyte. The following binary separations are also observed in other background electrolytes and the corresponding serial number of background electrolytes are given in the parenthesis :

W(VI) - Cr(VI) (No. i); Fe(CN)₆⁴⁻ - Fe(CN)₆³⁻ (No. iii); Fe(CN)₆⁴⁻ - SCN⁻ (No. V); V(V) - SCN⁻, W(VI) - Mo(VI), V(V) - Cr(VI), V(V) - Mo(VI), PO₄³⁻ - Cr(VI) (No. VII).

From the above results, it seems that electrophoresis on hydrated stannic oxide impregnated paper is of value in certain analytical separations that are not feasible on ordinary Whatman No. 1 papers.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to University Grants Commission (India) for a fellowship to one of the authors (U. G. C.), to Prof. A. K. De, Department of Chemistry, for constant encouragement.

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